

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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IMPLEMENTING EARLY MOBILIZATION IN THE INTENSIVE CARE UNIT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Early mobility (EM) is vital for patients in the intensive care unit (ICU), as prolonged bed rest can create further complications. Evidence suggests performing EM in the ICU benefits critically ill patients by reducing the incidence of ICU-Acquired Weakness (ICU-AW), decreasing the number of ventilator days, and decreasing the length of stay. Literature shows several barriers to mobility, including lack of standardized protocols, safety concerns, and lack of resources. Research shows that implementing an EM protocol provides positive benefits for ICU patients and has been adopted as part of a patient's care plan in hospitals and outside the United States. This quality improvement project aimed to modify an existing EM protocol using evidence-based practices and implementing the modified EM protocol in a medical ICU. Early mobility education was performed for one week. There was a 50% compliance rate of assessing patient's mobility that the MICU nurses performed. Using the PDSA cycle as a guide in accomplishing the project's purpose helped to identify barriers to performing EM in the MICU. Due to the high acuity of the ICU patients during the COVID-19 pandemic, this project's full implementation had some limitations. The recommendation for the future is to perform another PDSA cycle to address the barriers in performing EM. Developing a multidisciplinary early mobility team also influences EM implementation success.

Keywords: early mobility in the intensive care unit, progressive. mobility, ABCDEF Bundle, ICU Liberation, barriers to early mobility, ventilator days, ICU length of stay

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Background

Patients on bed rest who receive mechanical ventilation often suffer the effects of prolonged immobility, which can result in respiratory, cardiovascular, integumentary, and musculoskeletal complications (Dirkes & Kozlowski, 2019). Those in the intensive care unit (ICU) frequently develop muscle weakness related to the severity of their illness. Zhang et al. (2019) stated approximately 20% to 50% of critically ill patients in the ICU develop ICU-Acquired Weakness (ICU-AW). Patients with weak muscles are at risk for prolonged ventilation and a longer hospital stay. This increased length of stay (LOS) contributes to the development of iatrogenic outcomes, such as falls, ventilator-associated events (VAE), catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI), and pressure ulcers (Fraser et al., 2015). Finally, the long-term sequelae of muscle atrophy may include impaired functional status and the need for additional medical interventions even after being discharged from the hospital (Hashem et al., 2016).

Many researchers use the term early mobility (EM) interchangeably with progressive mobility. Henceforth, the project author will use the term EM in this paper. Falkenstein et al. (2020) defined mobility as a “multidisciplinary approach to increasing the patient participation in the upright activity and walking” (p. 29). While there is general agreement on EM definitions, implementing an EM process is challenging for many institutions. Barriers to EM are misperceptions of the process, limited resources to support its implementation, and lack of evidence-based protocols to guide nurses (Fontela et al., 2018; Fraser et al., 2015; Harrold et al., 2015).

Problem Statement

The majority of patients admitted to an ICU are placed on bed rest orders, which prevents them from getting out of bed, sitting in a chair, or ambulating. At the medical intensive care unit

(MICU) where the project author currently practices, patients are not mobilized per their capability because bed rest orders are not updated daily or re-assessed. Most patients are not progressively ambulated despite providing multiple educational in-services to the nursing staff on EM's importance. Nurses themselves identified many barriers to EM. These barriers included limited resources to assist with ambulation, insufficient time to implement the EM practices, high patient acuity levels, absence of physician support, and bed rest orders that are not updated, which is further discussed in the results section.

As seen in Figure 1, there is an existing EM protocol at the project facility's MICU. The current EM protocol consists of a continuum of five levels of mobilization. The first level involves engaging the patient in passive range of motions. The fifth level involves full ambulation. However, based on the project author's observations, EM of ventilated patients rarely occurs. A review of the nurses' documentation in the electronic medical record (EMR) shows that patients seldom progress from sitting in a chair, out of bed, and to ambulation.

Figure 1

Adult ICU Progressive Mobility Continuum

Note. Current Adult ICU Progressive Mobility Continuum used by ICU nurses as a guide in implementing progressive mobility in critically ill patients at the project facility.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to modify the project facility's progressive mobility protocol, implement the modified EM protocol using evidence-based practices, and evaluate the results of the change in improving the health outcomes of critically ill patients in the MICU at a Level I trauma hospital.

Project Objectives

There were four objectives to the project. The first objective was to identify and address barriers to EM in a medical ICU setting. The second objective was to review and modify the project facility's existing EM protocol using an evidence-based practice approach. The third objective was to implement and subsequently evaluate the modified EM protocol by identifying

when EM activities should be initiated and documenting the performed EM activity. The fourth objective was to collect outcome measures: the number of ventilator days, LOS, and the number of adverse events.

Supporting Framework

Practice change requires thoughtful planning and adequate preparation. The Institute for Healthcare Improvement's (IHI) Model for Improvement framework addresses fundamental elements needed in the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles, as seen in Figure 2. The model presents the three essential questions to answer when seeking improvement.

Figure 2

Model for Improvement Framework and PDSA Cycle

Note. IHI's Innovation Series (2003). Adapted from The Breakthrough Series: IHI's Collaborative Model for Achieving Breakthrough Improvement. Institute of Healthcare Improvement.

Stakeholders must understand the purpose of the change project to answer the first question regarding what is being accomplished. An explicit aim statement detailing the project's goal is to know whether a change is an improvement. The second question is answered by

identifying the appropriate measures by collecting and reviewing quantitative data to monitor progress. Finally, to answer the third question about what changes can be made to improve the problem, multiple PDSA cycles through iterative hypothesis testing and identifying changes that will meet the project's aim are completed. After the three questions are addressed and agreed upon by the team, changes are identified and tested using PDSA cycles.

The PDSA cycle will guide the modification and implementation of the EM protocol in the MICU. Christoff (2018) described the PDSA cycle as four steps completed in sequence. A problem is identified and addressed by changes to current practices, which are then measured and analyzed to determine if the change was effective. Additional modifications to the change can be made to ensure that the change was an improvement to the organization. If the change was not appropriate, the cycle could be modified until the change addresses the problem. The PDSA cycle allows small tests of change to improve a process, allowing a structured process to be followed (Coury et al., 2017).

Plan is the first step in the PDSA cycle, in which goals are developed that include action plans to test or observe any intervention (AHRQ, 2017b). Do is the second step, which is the implementation in the PDSA cycle. Study is the third step, where evaluation occurs. The fourth step is Act. The Act step is to make decisions to adopt or make additional changes to the intervention if needed. At this point, decisions are made to abandon the change or implement the change if found effective. Using the PDSA cycle concept will allow the project author to develop, implement, and evaluate EM protocol in the medical ICU. Figure 3 provides a visual representation of the PDSA cycle used in this project.

Figure 3*PDSA Cycle*

Note. PDSA Cycle to implement EM in the MICU

Plan Step

The planning step began with stakeholder identification. Stakeholders are members of the organization who believe that EM is essential. The stakeholders were the facility's organizational leadership consisting of hospital administrators, chief nursing officer, clinical nursing director, nurse manager, MICU nurse champion, and the ICU medical director. These stakeholders are vital to the project's success since they will execute policy change decisions and access resources.

Next in the Plan step was to schedule a meeting with the stakeholders to review the purpose. A clear understanding of what needs to be improved in the MICU was essential. The Plan also included a discussion of current literature on EM in the ICU setting. As seen in Appendices B and C, the daily and weekly EM collection tools were introduced and explained to

the clinical nursing director during the Plan step. The Plan step also included identifying MICU patients eligible to perform EM activities. An EMT was to be created that consists of a multidisciplinary team, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Early Mobility Team (EMT) and their Roles

Early Mobility Team Member	Roles
Primary Provider	Assess eligibility of patient Write order for EM activities Supervise EM activity
Primary ICU Nurse	Assess eligibility of patient Coordinate EM activity with EMT Perform EM activity Assess the safety of patient Document the activity in EMR Complete the DEMDC tool
Respiratory Care Practitioner	Assess eligibility of patient Coordinate with EMT Assess patient's respiratory status Monitor endotracheal or tracheostomy tube
Nursing Attendant	Assist patient with EM activities Provide support to the team
Project Author	Facilitate planning, implementation, and evaluation of EMT protocol Collect completed data collection tools Provide just-in-time training Present findings to the stakeholders Coordinate meetings to discuss success and areas that need improvement

Note. The Early Mobility Team participants, their roles and responsibilities

Literature on the topic was shared with the MICU nurses to increase their awareness of current ICU practices. Evidence-based protocols found in the literature highlighted the validity of using EM protocols in the MICU for improving patient care outcomes. The aim of identifying best practices in EM was to develop guidelines for adopting, implementing, and sustaining an EM protocol in the ICU. During the Plan step, the Daily Early Mobility Data Collection

(DEMDC) tool was presented to the MICU staff and guidelines on the data needed and how they would be used. Also, at this time, baseline data was shared with MICU nurses to compare current practices at the study facility with the supporting literature.

A timeline was created for the EMT to use as a guide outlining each step of the project's implementation. During social distancing, EMT meetings were conducted one-on-one. As seen in Appendix E, the AHRQ Nurse-Driven Early Mobility Protocol and the AHRQ's Medical Screening Algorithm, as seen in Appendix F, were shared with the MICU staff. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic and an incomplete EMT, the algorithm was not fully introduced. Reviewing this information with nurses allowed the staff to learn how other hospitals utilized EM activities. Lastly, dissemination of EM information was limited to small group in-services, in which the project author talked about and answered questions regarding the EM protocol.

Do Step

The Do step involved educating the EMT and nursing staff about AHRQ's nurse-driven early mobility protocol. Documenting the change process took place through the collection of data during the Do step. The DEMDC tool, as seen in Appendix A, and the WEMDC tool, as seen in Appendix B, were collected during the Do step. The data collection tools are further discussed in the data collection section of this project. Information gathered from this project will help direct appropriate steps for future PDSA cycles.

Study Step

The Study step is the third step of the PDSA cycle and is when data analysis occurs. Evaluation of the nurse's ability to implement EM happens during the study phase. In performing the PDSA cycle, Christoff (2018) suggested that each change should be tested one at a time on a smaller scale. This means that the initial PDSAs would include only one nurse and

one patient who would perform EM activities. The process would be evaluated to identify areas for improvement and adopt what worked. Another PDSA cycle would then be performed to prepare the next nurse to perform EM on a different patient eligible for EM activities. This process would continue until all ICU nurses and nursing attendants in the MICU had an opportunity to perform EM activities on all eligible patients until full implementation of EM protocol had been achieved.

In the Study step, the author reviewed whether there were any improvements after implementing the EM protocol. The number of ventilator days was continuously collected and plotted for three weeks on a run chart, then on a control chart as sufficient data became available. The project hypothesis was that the aggregate average of ventilator days would decrease as the number of patients mobilized increases. The run charts and control charts identified non-random or special cause variations to prove that the change was an improvement. A decrease in ventilator days would result in looking for non-random or special cause variations to show that the change was indeed an improvement.

Evaluating the LOS for patients in the MICU was completed during the Study step. In the Study step, the aggregated data collected before, during, and after project implementation provided information on ICU LOS. The data collected was plotted on a run chart, and when sufficient data became available, the collected data were plotted on a control chart. Implementing EM activities was projected to decrease ICU LOS days, and this would identify if EM activities benefitted the patients.

All feedback from the MICU nurses regarding the barriers to performing EM activities would be evaluated. The data on barriers to performing EM activities will be presented to the director of physical therapy since she was also seeking to implement a similar protocol. The

initial PDSA cycle identified barriers, and solutions were initiated to alleviate the barriers, improving the project facility's EM protocol. The data on the highest mobility activity the patients performed in the MICU would be collected. Finally, the observed positive change in the number of out-of-bed patients will demonstrate whether the project objectives have been achieved. Data will be analyzed with the stakeholders and illustrated through run charts, control charts, bar graphs, percentages, and visual analysis.

In this step, outcome measures, process measures, and balancing measures are identified. According to Povost and Murray (2011), process measures are indicators that will guide the researcher to determine whether the change implemented was an improvement. A balancing measure is the unintended effects of the implemented change (Provost & Murray, 2011).

Act Step

The Act is the last step of the PDSA cycle. In this step, the team and management stakeholders consider the outcomes, modify the protocol, and consider the appropriate next steps of implementation. Here, the changes that worked well during EM project implementation will be identified to decide what worked well. In addition, a decision to perform another PDSA cycle for the areas that did not work well would occur during this step. Data that show improvement in patient outcomes after implementing EM are necessary to support the change and expand the project to other ICUs. A discussion regarding what will be formally proposed as a practice change and any other identified barriers will occur during the Act step.

Review of Literature

A literature review was conducted to provide the foundation for this doctoral project. The following electronic database was searched: CINAHL, PubMed, EBSCO, Cochrane Library, IHI, and AHRQ. The key terms and concepts used to search the databases include “mobility,” “early mobility in the intensive care unit,” “early mobility,” “progressive mobility,” “early mobility in the ICU,” “ABCDEF Bundle,” “ICU Liberation,” “barriers to early mobility,” “benefits of early mobility,” “rehabilitation,” “length of stay,” and “implementation of EM in the ICU.” The search inclusion criteria were limited to publications from 2015 to the present, and articles which were not written in the English language and not available in full text were excluded.

Early mobility is vital for patients who are in the ICU. Early mobility is part of the *ICU Liberation ABCDEF Bundle* launched by the Society of Critical Care Medicine’s (SSCM) Clinical Practice Guideline (Barnes-Daly et al., 2018). The ABCDEF bundle includes interventions to improve the assessment, management of pain, breathing, sedation choice, EM and exercise, delirium, and family engagement (Barnes-Daly et al.). A review of the literature produced publications that addressed immobility with mechanically ventilated patients and the feasibility of implementing EM practices in the ICU setting.

The mobility of critically ill patients in the ICU is a challenging topic to address, as it is a multi-faceted one. Patients in the ICU are often in critical condition and challenging for the nurse to physically mobilize due to an endotracheal tube (Chohan et al., 2018; Harrold et al., 2015; Hashem et al., 2016). Literature suggests that there is no standard protocol for determining when it is appropriate to begin mobilization (da Costa Torres et al., 2017). Lastly, other factors impact patient outcomes for those on ventilators for prolonged periods. Some of these factors are ICU-Acquired Weakness (ICU-AW), increased ventilator days, and increased LOS.

ICU-Acquired Weakness

Critically ill patients admitted to the ICU typically have a standard bed rest order, restricting them from engaging in any physical activity. Prolonged bed rest promotes immobility and causes further complications (Fraser et al., 2015; Harrold et al., 2015; Hashem et al., 2016). One of the complications of immobility is the ICU-AW (Clarissa et al., 2019; Watanabe et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2019). Chohan et al. (2018) defined ICU-AW as a weakness that has no cause. Early mobility in critically ill patients decreased ICU-AW incidence (Clarissa et al., 2019; Watanabe et al., 2019, Zhang et al., 2019).

The MICU nurses at the project facility were not familiar with ICU-AW. Because ICU-AW is not a term that ICU nurses were not acquainted with, the EM team incorporated this topic during the Plan step as part of education on the definition, assessment, and monitoring of ICU-AW.

Ventilator Days

Patients who require mechanical ventilation are at risk for complications such as ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) (Selvan et al., 2017). The goal for critically ill patients is to be weaned off the ventilator as soon and safely as possible. Progressively weaning patients off the ventilator is accomplished by decreasing sedation. Hashem et al. (2016) and da Costa Torres et al. (2017) support the concept of promoting EM in critically ill patients to decrease the number of days they are on a mechanical ventilator.

In a study mentioned in the IHI on how to prevent ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP), the length of ventilator days decreased from 7.3 days to 4.9 days when sedation was interrupted. Patients are evaluated for the earliest moment to be weaned off the ventilator by performing Spontaneous Awakening Trial (SAT). When to begin SAT is determined through

collaboration with providers and nurses. Balas et al. (2019) stated that when SAT and Spontaneous Breathing Trial (SBT) is performed, patient outcomes are improved, resulting in fewer days on ventilators, fewer ventilator-associated events, and shorter days in the ICU.

Zhang et al. (2019) reviewed a conflicting report on two separate studies, wherein EM did not affect mechanical ventilation duration, but there was an increase in the number of ventilator-free days. According to Zhang and colleagues, the differing results could have been due to participant's inclusion criteria, in that all patients were included; the research did not concentrate on patients who were on mechanical ventilation. According to Klompas et al. (2015), a daily collaborated effort to assess patient's readiness to be weaned off the ventilator by performing interventions such as the spontaneous awakening trial (SAT) and spontaneous breathing trial (SBT) has shown a decrease in ventilator-associated events; therefore decreasing ventilator days which is one of the patient outcomes. Dirkes and Kozlowski (2019) mentioned that early mobility's positive effects in critically ill patients demonstrated a significant increase of ventilator-free days.

Prone therapy has been recommended to treat ICU patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome ([ARDS] Cannon et al., 2018; Morata et al., 2021; Wiggermann et al., 2020). Prone positioning has been found to reduce mortality to 17.4% compared with supine positioning (Morata et al., 2021). Prone positioning allows ventilation to parts of the lungs that are dependent, allowing gravity to drain secretions; therefore, improving ventilation when patients are turned from their backs to their abdomens. (Morata et al., 2021). Prone therapy can be achieved either manually or with specialty beds that automatically turn the patient. Although literature demonstrates that patients' movement from supine position to prone position can improve ventilation and reduce mortality, some barriers were identified. Positioning patients in a

prone position requires additional trained staff to prevent adverse events from happening, such as dislodgement of lines and tubes and hemodynamic instability (Wiggermann et al., 2020).

Length of Stay in the ICU

The longer a patient remains on a ventilator, the longer that patient will stay in the ICU. Da Costa Torres et al. (2017) examined the effects of EM on the functional status and LOS for patients undergoing coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) in a randomized controlled trial. They found that EM did decrease the LOS. However, research on the benefits of EM for patients on ventilators and its effect on LOS has been inconsistent (Doiron et al., 2018). One randomized control trial did not tie EM to the beneficial outcomes of physical function (Doiron et al.) Other studies have shown minimal variations in the ICU LOS, indicating the lack of supporting evidence that EM affects LOS (Chohan et al., 2018; Fraser et al., 2015).

Patients on ventilators tend to have various comorbidities, which makes it difficult to evaluate whether EM is beneficial. The research in this area varies on how EM is operationalized and which strategies are used to determine readiness to ambulate (Chohan et al., 2018; Fraser et al., 2015). Standardization of the methods used to determine EM and weaning readiness should be determined to evaluate the benefit of EM protocols (da Costa Torres et al., 2017).

Barriers to Implementing Early Mobility Protocols

A review of recent literature found that EM implementation results in positive outcome and it is feasible, and that there were also safety concerns when executing EM protocols in the ICU setting (Da Conceicao et al., 2017; Harrold et al., 2015; Hashem et al., 2016; Timenetsky et al., 2020). Safety concerns were centered on staff availability, healthcare members' perceptions, patients' acuity, and lack of standardization to measure EM activities (Fraser et al., 2015; Hodgson et al., 2018). Harshem et al. (2016) attributed it to the fact that staff are assigned to

other duties and have competing priorities. Significant barriers to implementing EM practices included patient safety issues and the lack of standardized protocols (Timenetsky et al., 2020).

Patient Safety Issues

Patient safety involves the patient's acuity level or hemodynamic status. Healthcare workers, such as nurses, providers, and physical therapists, collectively expressed patient safety as a general barrier when implementing EM practices (Chohan et al., 2018; Da Conceicao et al., 2017; Harrold et al., 2015; Hashem et al., 2016; Hickmann et al., 2016; Hodgson et al., 2018). Some researchers mentioned central lines, such as femoral catheters, as barriers to executing EM (Da Conceicao et al., 2017; Hashem et al., 2016). Harrold et al. (2015) identified the presence of an endotracheal tube as the reason for not implementing EM. Other research results (Hassan et al., 2017) concurred with this finding related to concerns about the patient's airway.

Sedation was noted as a significant barrier to implementing EM (Harrold et al., 2015; Hashem et al., 2016; Hodgson et al., 2018). According to Hashem et al. (2016), minimizing sedation can be collectively done with EM, but collaboration with the health care providers is essential. Care must be taken to assess the choice of sedatives, which might interfere with EM implementation. Limiting the use of benzodiazepines and, instead, selecting short-acting sedatives might result in more positive patient outcomes when using EM measures. Castro et al. (2015) also found that sedation was one of EM implementation barriers.

Lack of Standardized Protocol

Additional barriers to implementing EM practices were related to a standardized protocol. According to the literature, there is no standard protocol, but there are different interpretations of how this protocol should be carried out. Research supported the benefits of EM in the ICU, but these studies' focus differed. Da Costa Torres et al. (2017) studied physical exercise after cardiac

surgery and concluded that standardization was lacking in terms of what type of exercise should be done, how often the patient should exercise, the duration of time, and at what intensity. A study mentioned by Hodgson et al. (2018) addressed the lack of clarity that resulted, even while implementing an EM protocol that utilized SCCM's ICU Liberation ABCDEF Bundle. Finally, Hodgson and colleagues and da Costa Torres and colleagues mentioned that not having sufficient resources and care coordination were hindrances to standardized EM performance.

Successful Early Mobilization Programs

Early mobility programs have been implemented in several ICU settings, including at John Hopkins Hospital (medical ICU) and Shands Hospital at the University of Florida (Hashem et al., 2016). A study by Bakhru et al. (2015) found that 45% of hospitals in the United States perform EM practices in the ICU setting. These facilities found a decrease in LOS for patients in the ICU and the hospital in general when practicing EM (Hashem et al., 2016). Implementing EM programs in a hospital setting has also proven to be successful in countries outside of the United States. Saint-Luc University in Belgium (an urban facility in the United Kingdom) and eight tertiary hospitals in Japan showed decreased LOS for ICU patients when using EM as part of the treatment plan (Hickmann et al., 2016; Watanabe et al., 2019).

Hospitals implementing EM developed a multidisciplinary team to perform and oversee EM activities that contribute to their program's success. The literature supports a team approach to using the PDSA model (Chohan et al., 2018; Hashem et al., 2016; Hickmann et al., 2016; Polster, 2015; Watanabe et al., 2019). Based on EM literature, the project author decided to integrate both concepts to redesign its EM protocol. Using the PDSA model, the goal is to develop a multidisciplinary team to implement the EM protocol in the MICU. The multidisciplinary team is identified as EMT, as mentioned in Table 1.

Methods

The purpose of this project was to modify an existing progressive mobility protocol, implement the modified protocol in a MICU at the project facility, and then evaluate the modified protocol's effectiveness on patient outcomes.

For this DNP project, EM was defined as initiating progressive movement on patients who meet the project criteria. Progressive movement was defined as starting at a basic level that required minimal to no effort on the patient's part and then slowly advanced towards walking. The process was to begin with passive range of motion and then progress to sitting at the edge of the bed, then transferring from bed to chair, standing and finally ambulating, depending on the patient's ability and medical status. In this project, MICU nurses assessed all critically ill adult patients admitted to the MICU and those on mechanical ventilators to determine if they were candidates for EM. Initiation of EM started within 48 hours of their admission to the MICU.

Design

A quality improvement approach was used to meet the project's goals. The IHI Model for Improvement Framework and PDSA model guided all aspects of this project.

Setting

The project was implemented in a 20-bed MICU at a Level I trauma hospital. This large urban academic medical center is considered a safety net for the most underserved in the Los Angeles area.

Participants

Thirty-eight ICU nurses participated in this project. During the individual meetings, the project author explained the quality improvement (QI) project to each nurse. The ICU nurses

who participated in the project were 18 years and older and worked in the MICU for at least one year. The nurses were informed of the risks and benefits of their involvement in the project.

Institutional Review Board Approval

Institutional review board (IRB) approval from California State University, Los Angeles, was secured before the project commenced at the study facility, as shown in Appendix C.

Measures

Outcome measures were used to determine whether there was an improvement from the education that was provided to nurses regarding EM. Outcome measures were LOS in the ICU, the number of ventilator days, and the highest mobility level achieved at discharge or transfer from the ICU. Indicators were the percentage of patients mobilized each day and the number of barriers to performing EM. Balancing measures were identified as adverse events for patients, as seen in Table 2. Data for each of these measures were recorded on run charts beginning one week before implementing the education to obtain baseline data and ending one week after implementation. Data were converted to control charts once sufficient data was available.

Table 2

Measures: Outcome Measures, Process Measures, and Balancing Measures

Type of measure	Measure name	Measure description
Outcome	Average Length of Stay (LOS) in the MICU	<p>For each eligible patient discharged, the discharge date will be subtracted from the admission date to get the total length of stay in the MICU</p> <p>For the outcome measure, the average LOS will be recorded</p> <p>Numerator: The total length of stay for all discharged patients</p> <p>Denominator: All discharged patients that week</p> <p>Result: Average LOS for the week. This will be recorded on a run chart</p> $\text{LOS}_{\text{total}} / \text{Patients}_{\text{total}}$
	Average Ventilator Days	Total number of ventilator days from the first day of intubation to the day of extubation collected for one week aggregated and recorded on a run chart
	Highest Level of Mobility achieved	The average highest level of mobility achieved for sample patients prior to implementation will be compared to the average highest level of mobility achieved for a sample of patients post-implementation
Process	Initiation of Mobility	<p>Total number of eligible patients mobilized will be collected daily</p> <p>Numbers will be aggregated for one week and displayed using a run chart as a percentage with the number of patients mobilized that day divided by the total number of eligible patients</p>
	Barriers to Mobility	Documentation of actual barriers to performing mobilization will be recorded by MICU nurses and collected daily at a

Type of measure	Measure name	Measure description
Outcome	Average Length of Stay (LOS) in the MICU	<p>For each eligible patient discharged, the discharge date will be subtracted from the admission date to get the total length of stay in the MICU</p> <p>For the outcome measure, the average LOS will be recorded</p> <p>Numerator: The total length of stay for all discharged patients</p> <p>Denominator: All discharged patients that week</p> <p>Result: Average LOS for the week. This will be recorded on a run chart</p> <p>$LOS_{total}/Patients_{total}$</p> <p>specific time. The type of barriers aggregated daily will be displayed using a run chart</p>
Balancing	Number of Adverse Events	The total number of adverse events during the stay in the MICU while performing EM

Note. Outcome measures were LOS in the ICU, ventilator days, and the highest level of mobility achieved upon discharge or transfer from the ICU. Process measures were initiation of mobility and barriers to mobility. Balancing measure was the number of adverse events during mobilization.

Outcome Measures

Length of Stay in the ICU

The ICU LOS to be documented using the data collection tool averaged across patients, as seen in Appendix B. The LOS data was collected over 21 days. The data was collected one week before educating the ICU nurses, during just-in-time training, and one week after providing the EM education. Eligible patients' LOS was determined based on admission to the MICU until discharge or transfer from the MICU. This information was to be recorded on a run chart.

Ventilator Days

Measuring ventilator days was conducted by identifying the average number of ventilator days on mechanically ventilated patients admitted to the MICU. The data was extracted from the data collection tools starting one week before, during, and following EM education. All patient data was to be aggregated weekly and displayed using a run chart.

Highest Level of Mobility

The project goal was to mobilize patients early on, for the purpose of improving their functional status, activity level, respiratory status, and for decreasing ventilator days and LOS in the ICU (Schujmann et al., 2019). The AHRQ levels of mobility were used to identify the highest mobility level. The mobility levels were to be identified from 0 to 10, as seen in Table 3. Patients who could walk while in the MICU were considered at the highest level of mobility. The documented number of patients who were mobilized and their highest level of mobility was collected daily. The average number of the highest level of mobility was aggregated for one week during the education. The mean score was to be compared before and after the EM education.

Table 3

Mobility Level

Highest Level of Mobility	Description
0	Nothing: Passive movement, no active participation from the patient. Activities include passively turning, passive range of motion exercises
1	Transfer from bed to chair without standing Transferring from bed to chair without standing with assistance, such as hoist, lift, or sliding patient from bed to chair.
2	Sitting/Dangling at the edge of the bed Sitting or dangling the patient's legs at the edge of the bed with or without assistance.
3	Standing

	Standing in place, applying weight on both feet, with or without assistance.
4	Transfer from bed to chair with standing Transferring from bed to chair by being able to step or shuffle involves lifting one leg to another to move from bed to chair or chair to bed.
5	Marching in place Marching in place is the ability of the patient to lift each foot alternately, with or without assistance.
6	Walking The highest level of activity the patient can perform—the patient’s ability to walk away from the bed or the chair with or without assistance.

Note. The highest level of activity would be documented by nurses daily. Early mobility guide for reducing ventilator-associated events in mechanically ventilated patients: data collection tools. *AHRQ Publication, 16(17)*, 1 – 28.

Process Measures

Data was collected for the eligible patients who were mobilized. At the same time each day, the project author collected the DEMDC tool data (as described in the supporting framework section in the Do step of the PDSA cycle) to identify which patients had been mobilized. The data were aggregated and recorded in percentage on a run chart, with the numerator being the number of patients mobilized to any level and the denominator included all eligible patients. Upon discharge, information on the highest level of mobility achieved was recorded on the data collection tool. The mean scores of the highest mobility level achieved prior to the EM education were compared to the mean scores of the mobility highest level achieved post-education.

Barriers to Mobility

A count of the barriers that interfered with achieving the highest mobility level was calculated based on nurses’ perceptions. The nurses documented the reasons eligible patients were not mobilized using the DEMDC tool. The data were recorded as barriers and were

collected at the same time each day. The goal was to find solutions to reduce the number of these barriers.

Balancing Measures

Adverse events were documented on the DEMDC tool based on the type that occurred. The total number of adverse events was to be recorded on a run chart. These adverse events were additionally given a code to denote their type, using the modified AHRQ event codes in Table 4.

Table 4

Adverse Events

Types	Description
A	No adverse events occurred
B	Endotracheal or tracheostomy dislodgement
C	Feeding tubes dislodgement: nasogastric, orogastric, or percutaneous feeding tubes
D	Line displacement: Peripheral and central line catheters. Central line catheters include triple lumen catheters, vascular access catheter, pulmonary artery catheter, arterial line, and peripheral inserted central catheter.
E	Device dislodgement Devices other than lines, feeding tubes, endotracheal tube or tracheostomy tube. Examples: pacemaker wires, chest tubes, and wound vacuum machines.
F	Fall This means that a fall acquired by the patient with or without the assistance of the staff
G	Cardiac arrest
H	Death
I	Other Other adverse events that occurred but not listed above

Note. Daily Data Collection Tools. Adapted from Early Mobility Guide for Reducing Ventilator-Associated Events in Mechanically Ventilated Patients.

Procedures

This section describes the actions taken to implement this DNP project. It provides the details behind the project implementation and data collection processes.

Approval

Organizational leadership and IRB approval were secured before the project commenced. Key stakeholders were identified for this QI project. Appendix E presents a signed letter of approval from the chief nursing officer at the project facility granting approval. Verbal support was obtained from the ICU clinical nursing director, ICU medical director, and MICU nurse manager.

Processes

In this QI project, the project author wanted to implement a modified EM protocol in the ICU. A small test of change was implemented using the PDSA cycle as a guide to attain the clinical objectives. Data were collected, aggregated, and displayed in run charts, control charts, and bar graphs. The data were collected through chart reviews of the patients' EMR and gathering the data collection tools from the MICU nurses who participated in this QI project.

The first PDSA cycle was completed using the PDSA worksheet shown in Appendix C. In the Plan step, key stakeholders were informed of the project. The stakeholders were the clinical nursing director, MICU attending physician, MICU nurse manager, and the MICU nurses. They were informed about the project, the purpose, and the time the project would commence and end. The project author developed a PowerPoint presentation which was used for EM education and was shared with the MICU attending physician. The data collection tools and PowerPoint presentation were also sent to the MICU attending physician for her information.

The ABCDEF bundle, ICU Liberation, and SAT (as discussed in the review of literature) were discussed to aid in facilitating EM practices during the monthly ICU Medical Director's meeting. This meeting was held at the facility, included the ICU medical director, attending physicians of all services, ICU clinical nursing director, nurse managers, and the project author.

Discussions with a multidisciplinary team on developing the EM nurse-led protocol for the ICU were in progress simultaneously. The multidisciplinary team included the physical therapy department's chief director, MICU clinical nursing director, and the lead for the EM project in the medical-surgical unit. The plan was to use the medical-surgical unit's EM protocol as a guide to be modified according to the ICU needs. The current ICU progressive mobility protocol, the medical-surgical EM protocol, AHRQ nurse-driven EM protocol, and screening criteria for eligible patients for EM were also discussed.

In the Do step of the PDSA cycle, the project author provided MICU nurses with Just-in-time (JITT) training on EM using a PowerPoint created by the project author. The education was initiated face to face and conducted one on one in the early morning, due to COVID-19 restrictions. The EM education was also included during small morning huddles to discuss EM activities. The project author performed unit rounds in the morning and in the afternoon to provide support and answer questions for one week during the EM education.

The MICU nurse collected a list of eligible patients for EM activities, using the DEMDC and WEMDC tools. Lists included all adult patients admitted to the MICU, whether non-ventilated or mechanically ventilated. Each MICU nurse received a list of criteria by which patients were excluded from EM activities, as seen in Appendix A. Patients who were excluded from participating in EM were on comfort care, had an unstable airway, or were monitored for ICP. Of note, patients were also to be excluded if they were diagnosed in the previous 48 hours

with post-cardiac arrest, myocardial infarction, newly diagnosed stroke, actively being treated for seizures, and spine and skeletal diagnoses.

In the Study step of the first PDSA cycle, the data from the DEMDC and the WEMDC tools were collected. The data collected pertained to the MICU patients' number of ventilator days, ICU LOS, the highest level of mobility, number of eligible patients mobilized, barriers to implementing EM activities, and any adverse events. The results were aggregated and displayed in run charts and control charts.

In the Act step of the PDSA, the results were examined for areas of possible improvement. Since this DNP project was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic, it was anticipated that this could impact the results of this QI project.

Discussions took place with the clinical nursing director of the ICU and other attending physicians to promote the use of appropriate sedation in the ICU during this study. A Spontaneous Awakening Trial (SAT) protocol was used to guide ICU nurses to perform a daily SAT screening and trial to assess patients' readiness to be weaned off the mechanical ventilator. The SAT protocol was developed and approved by the appropriate committee.

Data Collection

The DEMDC and the WEMDC were used to collect the data for the EM project. An ICU nurse for each patient documented on this DEMDC tool, and the project author collected it each day. The project author additionally collected any needed data if the WEMDC tool was incomplete.

WEMDC Tool

The project author developed a WEMDC tool as seen in Appendix B, to document the patient's age, diagnoses, eligibility, LOS, admission and discharge dates, ventilator days,

intubation and extubation dates, as well as highest level of mobility performed that week. The WEMDC tool was completed by reviewing the patient's EHR a week before the EM education, during, and after EM education. The WEMDC tool was initiated one week before the EM education started for baseline data, and was used during the week of EM education, and one week after the EM education for comparison purposes.

Data documented in the WEMDC tool were the patient's age, the date the patient was eligible, the patient's diagnosis, admission and discharge dates, the intubation and extubation dates, and the highest level of mobility the patient achieved before discharge. The admission and discharge dates were needed to display the average patient LOS in the MICU. Intubation and extubation dates were necessary to show the average number of ventilator days. During the patient's stay in the MICU, the highest level of activity was extracted from the EHR.

DEMDC Tool

The DEMDC tool included the collection date, eligible patients who received EM activities, patient's baseline mobility, the highest level of activity the patient performed, adverse events, and the reason why patients were not mobilized. The highest level of activity and adverse events were noted. The DEMDC tool was given to those ICU nurses who had assigned patients each day. Education was provided to the MICU nurse on the benefits and purpose of EM. Each MICU nurse was also informed of how to fill out the data collection tool.

The project author was available for questions and additional training as needed. The inclusion and exclusion criteria were explained to each MICU nurse. Each ICU nurse documented eligible patients, the patient's baseline mobility, and whether the patient mobilized that day. A "Yes" or "No" answer was documented for each eligible patient. The tool also allowed the ICU nurse to document the reason their patient was not mobilized. The MICU nurse

documented the highest level of activities and also documented if any adverse events occurred while performing EM activities.

Results

The initial steps of the EM project were accomplished in three weeks. A review of the patients' charts who were admitted to the MICU from January 29, 2021, until February 23, 2021, was completed. Thirty-eight MICU nurses participated during the week of EM education, which was started on February 9, 2021, and ended on February 16, 2021. MICU nurses assessed their assigned patients daily for eligibility in performing EM activities. All patients in the MICU had a diagnosis of COVID-19. Most patients diagnosed with COVID-19 had secondary diagnoses of acute respiratory failure with hypoxemia and shortness of breath. The demographics of the patient population are displayed in Table 5.

Table 5

Patient Population

Demographics	Pre-EM Education January 29, 2021 to February 4, 2021 <i>n</i>	During EM Education February 9, 2021 to February 16, 2021 <i>n</i>	Post-EM Education February 16, 2021 to February 23, 2021 <i>n</i>
Gender			
Female	11	5	7
Male	19	19	14
Age	23 yrs. - 85 yrs.	27 yrs. - 87 yrs.	41 yrs. - 88 yrs.
Average	63 yrs.	61 yrs.	67 yrs.
MICU Patients	30	24	21
Excluded Patients	5	2	2
Comfort Care	3	2	1
s/p Cardiac Arrest	2	0	0
Cord Compression	0	0	1

Note. Demographics of the patients admitted to the MICU from January 29, 2021, to February 23, 2021.

Baseline data were collected for seven days, which was one week before the EM education was initiated. A total of 30 patients were admitted to the MICU from January 29, 2021, until February 4, 2021. Of the 30 patients, 11 were females, and 19 were males. The ages

of the 30 patients ranged from 23 to 85 years, with an average age of 63. Five patients were excluded from the study due to comfort care status or for being status-post cardiac arrest.

The EM education was conducted for seven days and took place from February 9, 2021, until February 16, 2021. There was no data collected on February 15, 2021, due to it being a holiday. During the EM education, there were a total of 24 patients admitted to the MICU. Out of the 24 patients, two patients were excluded because they were placed on comfort care. There were five females and 19 males admitted to the MICU this week. The ages ranged from 28 years old to 87 years old, with 61 years of age as the average.

One week after the EM education was initiated, data were collected for seven days from February 17, 2021 to February 23, 2021. During this week, there were a total of 21 patients admitted to the MICU. Two patients were excluded this week: one patient was diagnosed with cord compression, and the other patient was placed on comfort care. The patients' ages admitted to the MICU this week were from 41 years of age to 88 years of age. The average age was 67 years. There were seven females and 14 males who were admitted to the MICU this week.

Average Length of Stay in the MICU

The average LOS in the MICU was collected for 21 days, from January 29, 2021, to February 23, 2021. When patients were discharged, their average LOS was calculated and plotted on the run chart. Twenty-four patients were discharged or transferred from the MICU during these three weeks. In the run chart, the median average LOS was 6.9 days, as seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4*Average Length of Stay in MICU*

Note: A run chart that displays the average LOS of patients in the MICU.

The run chart was converted to a control chart to understand the data distribution better. The average LOS showed a mean length of stay of 9.6, as seen in Figure 5. It also showed the same patient on February 22, 2021, having an increased number of days in the MICU. In Figure 5, the range for the length of stay was 0 to 27 days, with a mean of 9.6. An XmR chart was used to represent all discharged patients' average length of stay in the MICU, as seen in Figure 6. The range for the length of stay of all MICU patients was 14 to 21 days, with a mean of 17.4.

Figure 5

Average Length of Stay of Discharged Patients in the MICU: X Chart

Figure 6

Length of Stay of All MICU Patients

Note: An X-chart showing the average LOS of all patients in the MICU from January 29, 2021, to February 23, 2021.

Ventilator Days Average

The average number of ventilator days was collected for three weeks on patients who were mechanically ventilated. The project author collected data from the EMR and documented the patients in the MICU, the patient's intubation date, and extubation dates. Data were collected for three weeks, starting from January 29, 2021, to February 4, 2021, and February 9, 2021 to February 23, 2021, and plotted in a run chart as shown in Figure 7. Each day for three weeks, the days of mechanical ventilation for each patient were aggregated and divided by the total number of patients on mechanical ventilators. A total of 2,176 ventilator days were documented for 221 patients, as seen in Figure 7. As a result, the average ventilator day was 10, as seen in Figure 8. These data were converted to control charts for a better understanding of their distribution.

In Figure 9, starting with the data point for February 15, 2021, a special cause variation (a trend) was observed. The average ventilator days were trending up starting on February 15, 2021, as seen in Figure 9. The new control limits established an increase in the average ventilator days from 8.2 to 13.5, indicating a statistically significant increase in the average ventilator days, as seen in Figure 9.

Figure 7

Total Number of Ventilator Days in the MICU

Note. The run chart shows the number of ventilator days for all patients each day. The number of ventilator days was collected for three weeks, from January 29, 2021 to February 23, 2021.

Figure 8*Average Ventilator Days in MICU*

Note. The run chart displays the average number of ventilator days for each patient plotted each day. The data was collected for three weeks, starting from January 29, 2021, until February 23, 2021.

Figure 9*Average Ventilator Days in MICU: X Chart***Highest Level of Mobility**

Patients' charts were reviewed for the documented highest level of mobility from January 29, 2021 to February 23, 2021. The highest level of activity was from "0," in which there were no EM activities performed. The majority of the patient's current activity documentation was noted to be "bed rest," in which no EM activities were implemented. One week before the EM education, all patients' charts had documentation of "bed rest." EM education was started on February 9, 2021, and during this week, a total of eight patients were mobilized. During this week, there were two patients who performed walking as the highest level of mobility; four patients were documented to be sitting or dangling at the edge of the bed; and one patient performed transferring from chair to bed without standing, as seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10

Highest Level of Mobility

Note. The number of MICU patients who achieved the highest level of activity.

Initiation of Mobility

Early mobility education took place from February 9, 2021, to February 16, 2021. Just-in-time training was performed face to face with the MICU nurses. The JITT training is further defined in the discussion section of this project. Each day, the MICU nurses who participated in the project identified patients who were eligible based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. A total of 104 MICU patients met the criteria to be part of the EM project, but only 57 patients were assessed for EM activities by the MICU nurses who participated in this project. This resulted in 50% of the total patients as seen in Figure 11. Of the 57 patients, only seven patients had EM activities performed, which resulted in 12% of patients in the MICU being mobilized, as seen in Figure 12.

Figure 11

Eligible Patients Assessed for Mobility

Note. A run chart that displays the percentage of eligible patients who were assessed for mobility.

Figure 12*Mobilized Patients*

Note. A run chart that displays the percentage of patients in which EM activities were performed.

Barriers to Mobility

Barriers to performing EM activities were documented using the DEMDC tool, as seen in Figure 13. There were 57 patients who were assessed daily for EM activities for one week, with only five patients who performed EM activities. The MICU nurses documented why the rest of the patients did not perform EM activities. There were five options: limited time, hemodynamically unstable, presence of lines/tubes, limited resources, and other. Limited time was documented once, 29 of the patients were hemodynamically unstable, 18 patients had lines and or tubes, and 11 were documented as having limited resources. There were 21 responses under other reason for not mobilizing patients. In the “Other” reasons, MICU nurses specified why patients were not mobilized. There were 13 responses that stated the patients were receiving sedation therapy. Four patients were on medication, requiring them to be paralyzed to assist with

their respiratory function and be manually prone. Another response from the MICU nurses for not mobilizing patients was that one of their patients had an altered consciousness level, secondary to being “status-post-procedure.” Lastly, one other response was that a patient had a pulmonary embolism that prevented the patient from performing EM activities.

Figure 13

Barriers in Implementing EM Activities

Note. The bar graph shows the number of documented reasons why patients were not mobilized.

Discussion

In this QI project, the project author wanted to implement EM activities in a medical ICU. A pilot test was conducted using the PDSA cycle as a guide to attain the clinical objectives. Data were collected, aggregated, and displayed in run charts, control charts, and bar graphs. The data were collected through chart review of the patients' EMR and gathering data collection tool information from the MICU nurses who participated in this study.

The COVID-19 pandemic resulted in a hospital-wide increase in patient admissions, and the MICU was significantly affected by an increase in critically ill patients. The surge in patients with COVID-19 required that nurses be assigned to two extremely critical patients, when under normal circumstances a nurse would have been assigned to only one severely critically ill patient. This caused an increase in patient workloads, and nurses were not able to participate in the project entirely. Overall, there was not enough staff to support implementing the modified EM protocol.

Although an EMT, as seen in Table 1 was to have been created, forming an entire team was not possible due to the COVID-19 pandemic and a shortage of staffing resources. As a result, only the MICU nurse and the project author were part of the team. A medical provider, a respiratory care practitioner, and a nursing attendant did not end up being part of the EM team.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, a part of the PDSA cycle was not implemented. The need to create an EMT was briefly discussed with the clinical nursing director but was subsequently not created. This was due to a shortage of staff and other competing priorities that needed to be addressed, such as the conversion of medical-surgical units to a progressive care unit to accommodate COVID-19 patients who required continuous monitoring.

The ICU nurses performed EM activities as part of the standard practice of care for MICU patients. During the week of EM education, MICU nurses assessed all critically ill patients, 18 years and older, and the patient's ability to be mobilized. In addition, an assessment of all MICU patients included patients who were either mechanically or nonmechanically ventilated. The ICU mobility protocol excluded adult patients who had orders for comfort care. Patients who required monitoring of their intracranial pressure were excluded. Patients who were a status-post cardiac arrest, diagnosed with stroke, and having had a myocardial infarction within the previous 48 hours were additionally excluded. Lastly, conditions of the spine and skeletal systems excluded patients from having EM performed.

Literature on the topic was shared with the MICU nurses to increase their awareness of current ICU practices. Evidence-based protocols found in the literature highlighted the validity of using EM protocols in the MICU for improving patient care outcomes. The aim of identifying best practices in EM was to develop guidelines for adopting, implementing, and sustaining an EM protocol in the ICU. During the Plan step, the Daily Early Mobility Data Collection (DEMDC) tool was presented to the MICU staff along with guidelines on the data needed and how they would be used. At this time, baseline data was shared with MICU nurses to compare current practices at the study facility with the supporting literature.

Due to the COVID-19 surge at the project author's facility, there were limitations in performing EM activities. The data collected was affected and did not provide an accurate representation of the effects of EM on the MICU patients. All patients in the MICU were diagnosed with COVID-19, with a secondary diagnosis of acute respiratory failure with hypoxemia and shortness of breath. For those reasons, the patients' respiratory status were

compromised, resulting in the need for supplemental oxygenation and physical activity restrictions to save their oxygen reserves.

The results did not show any changes in LOS of discharged patients and number of ventilator days for mechanically ventilated patients because of EM. The number of ventilator days was actually increased in week three of the project because patients remained in the ICU longer, requiring the need for oxygen support. An increase in patients admitted to the MICU on ventilators, as seen in Figure 4, can be attributed to this trend. A trend is identified when six or more consecutive data points increase or decrease (Provost & Murray, 2011). Because there were fewer than 20 data points, the control limits should be considered trial limits. Trial limits were used to calculate data points less than 20 to identify improvement areas or any undesired outcomes (Provost & Murray, 2011). When a special cause is identified, control limits need to be adjusted to establish the new average and range of the data set. A special cause indicates a change in the process occurred.

The LOS of patients in the MICU increased as a direct reflection of the patients' increasing acuity levels, requiring them to stay longer in the ICU for continuous monitoring. In Figure 4, one of the data points represents an astronomical point and is attributed to the one patient who was discharged on that day. An astronomical point is one that is visually unusual and does not fit into the data set (Provost & Murray, 2011). An XmR chart was used to represent the average length of stay of all discharged patients in the MICU, as seen in Figure 5. An XmR chart is beneficial when the data is plotted over time, and the variation of the data at one point is not as significant compared to the variation of data over a period of time (Provost & Murray, 2011).

When using a control chart, control limits represent the statistical range of the data set

The outcome from the EM education provided by the project author did not change the MICU nurses' practices. The *Just-in-time-training* (JITT) method was used to provide EM education to MICU nurses who participated in the DNP study. According to Peebles et al. (2020), JITT is a learning method that has been used in "staff training in quality improvement" that provides training and education in the setting. JITT was used to emphasize EM training in the clinical setting in the MICU.

The EM education and the documentation needed for data collection served as a reminder for the MICU nurses to evaluate their patient's mobility activities. The EM education did not change the nurses' practice, as reflected in the lack of EM activities performed a week after the EM education. The results suggested that EM education did not cause the MICU nurses to incorporate mobility practices into the care of their patients. The reported barriers by the MICU nurses prevented EM activities from being performed on the patients.

The use of a visual management board was part of the EM implementation and served as a means to communicate to patients and the EMT about the patient's daily mobility activities. However, nurses were limited in their ability to use the visual management board to document whether the patient was mobilized, as it was inside the patient's room. The restrictions placed on COVID-19 patients limited the nurse's time in the room to only tasks that were critical to the patient's needs.

Limitations

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in an overwhelming burden on most hospitals. The MICU unit at the project author's facility was one of the first units converted to a COVID-19 ICU. The MICU was inundated with increased admissions of patients who were diagnosed with COVID-19. These patients were admitted to the MICU because of their increased need for

oxygen, requiring continuous monitoring of their oxygen level. Because of their hemodynamic instability, the majority of the patients required a mechanical ventilator for oxygen support.

The patients' unusual high acuity added to the already exhausted ICU nurses in this unit, making it challenging to consistently include EM activities as part of patients' daily care. The MICU experienced shortages in staffing resources, such as a turn team or ancillary nurses who can assist with mobility activities. Respiratory care practitioners also experienced severe shortages, making collaboration to mobilize patients on a ventilator not feasible.

The patients' safety and the hospital personnel were prioritized. The surge of COVID-19 patients restricted hospital personnel from performing unessential activities. There was also a limitation of staff going into a COVID-19 patient's room to decrease exposure and possible viral transmission.

Recommendations

The MICU nurses who participated in the EM project implementation were aware of the benefits of EM. Multiple in-service training sessions have been provided to the MICU nurses about EM over the years. The ICU medical director addresses parts of the ABCDEF bundles in management meetings and during brief huddles with the ICU nurses. The sections of the ABCDEF bundle that are constantly discussed are the assessment and choice of pain medication, SAT and SBT, the choice of sedation, EM, and family engagement. The assessment of delirium as part of the ABCDEF bundle has been discussed briefly but not practiced by the ICU nurses. As mentioned, EM has been introduced to the ICU nurses many times but has not been incorporated into patients' daily care plans.

As the COVID-19 pandemic improves, the implementation of this EM QI project can be trialed once again. Currently, EM is part of discussions among the multidisciplinary team,

including the physical therapy department's chief director and the DHS ICU medical directors. The formation of an EMT is critical to implementing this project, planning and facilitating meetings, providing training, and circulating the benefit of EM in the ICU. The EM implementation requires a multidisciplinary approach to address it, which was impeded by the pandemic and was identified as a barrier.

Currently, the MICU collaborates with medical directors, medical attending, nursing leadership, and respiratory leadership in promoting screening patients on ventilators to interrupt their use of sedation by turning the sedation off daily. It allows the nurse to assess the patient's sedation level, which is one step in patients being weaned off the ventilator safely. The limitation of sedation use on mechanically ventilated patients can address one of the barriers of EM.

A decrease in patient's LOS and days on ventilators is expected after full EM project implementation. The project author identified the reasons ICU nurses were not performing EM activities. Recognizing the barriers nurses documented helps complete the next PDSA cycle to find ways to remove barriers.

Conclusion

This QI project aimed to modify the current EM protocol and implement the modified evidence-based nurse-driven protocol in the ICU setting. The goal was to incorporate EM activities into all ICU patients' daily care. The COVID-19 pandemic was a decisive factor that restricted this project's full implementation. One other aspect of a successful implementation and adoption of EM in the ICU is the involvement and support of a multidisciplinary team, including nurse leaders, providers, a physical therapist, respiratory therapist, ICU nurses, and ancillary staff. The benefit of performing EM activities among eligible ICU patients should not be undervalued. Allowing patients to resume as close to their highest mobility level before their ICU admission should be considered a priority in caring for ICU patients, as EM improves LOS, ventilator days, and hospital-acquired infections and improves patients' well-being and satisfaction.

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APPENDIX A

Daily Early Mobility Data Collection Tool

DAILY EARLY MOBILITY COLLECTION TOOL					
DATE:					
ELIGIBLE PATIENTS	BASELINE MOBILITY	DID PT. MOBILIZE? YES/NO	IF NO, WHY NOT?	HIGHEST LEVEL OF ACTIVITY: 0 - 6	ADVERSE EVENTS

Note: Eligible Patients: All adult, critically ill patients who are nonmechanically ventilated and on mechanical ventilators. Excluded are patients who are on comfort care, unstable airway; ICP monitoring, newly diagnosed in the previous 48 hours of myocardial infarction, newly diagnosed stroke in the previous 48 hours; status post-cardiac arrest in the previous 48 hours, active seizures, and spin/skeletal diagnosis that prevents them from performing EM activities.

Highest Level of Mobility: 0 = Nothing; 1 = Transfer from bed to chair without standing; 2 = Sitting / Dangling at the edge of the bed; 3 = Standing; 4 = Transfer from bed to chair with standing; 5 = Marching in place; and 6 = Walking.

Adverse Events: A = No adverse event occurred; B = Endotracheal/Tracheostomy dislodgement; C = Feeding tube dislodgement; D = Line displacement (peripheral and central line catheters); E = Device dislodgement (chest tube, pacemakers wires, etc.); F = Fall; G = Cardiac arrest; H = Death; I = Other

ELIGIBLE PATIENTS:

- All critically ill patients who are nonmechanically ventilated and on mechanical ventilators

EXCLUDED PATIENTS: Patients who are:

- On comfort care
- ICP monitoring
- Newly diagnosed within the last 48 hours of myocardial infarction
- Newly diagnosed stroke within the last 48 hours
- Status-post cardiac arrest within the last 48 hours
- Active seizures
- Spinal / Skeletal diagnosis

REASON FOR “NO”:

1. Limited Time
2. Hemodynamically Unstable
3. Presence of lines/tubes
4. Limited Resources
5. Other

HIGHEST LEVEL OF ACTIVITY:

- 0 – Nothing
- 1 – Transfer from bed to chair without standing
- 2 – Sitting / Dangling at the edge of the bed
- 3 – Standing
- 4 – Transfer from bed to chair with standing
- 5 – Marching in place
- 6 – Walking

ADVERSE EVENTS:

- A – Nothing
- B – Endotracheal / Tracheostomy dislodgement
- C – Feeding tube dislodgement
- D – Line displacement (peripheral and central line catheters)
- E – Device dislodgement (chest tube, pacemaker wires, etc.)
- F – Fall
- G – Cardiac arrest
- H – Death
- I – Other

APPENDIX B

Weekly Early Mobility Data Collection Tool

WEEKLY EARLY MOBILITY DATA COLLECTION TOOL							
DATE:							
DC PATIENTS AGE	ELIGIBILITY DATE	DIAGNOSIS	LENGTH OF STAY		VENTILATOR DAYS		HIGHEST LEVEL OF MOBILITY 0 - 6
			ADMISSION DATE	DISCHARGE DATE	INTUBATION DATE	EXTUBATION DAY	
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							
7							
8							
9							
10							
11							
12							
13							
14							
15							
16							
17							
18							
19							
20							

Note: Highest Level of Mobility: 0 = Nothing; 1 = Transfer from bed to chair without standing; 2 = Sitting / Dangling at the edge of the bed; 3 = Standing; 4 = Transfer from bed to chair with standing; 5 = Marching in place; and 6 = Walking.

APPENDIX C

Nurse-Driven Early Mobility Protocol

Note. Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (2017). Adapted from Nurse-Driven Early Mobility Protocols: Facilitator Guide.

<https://www.ahrq.gov/hai/tools/mvp/modules/technical/nurse-early-mobility-protocols-fac=guide.html>

APPENDIX D

Medical Screening Algorithm to Assess Appropriateness of Rehabilitation

Note. Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (2017). Adapted from Nurse-Driven Early Mobility Protocols: Facilitator Guide.

<https://www.ahrq.gov/hai/tools/mvp/modules/technical/nurse/early-mobility-protocols-fac-guid.html>

APPENDIX E

IRB Approval

Office Memorandum

DATE:	January 29, 2021
TO:	Raymond Gantioque
FROM:	Claire Bakewell
PROJECT TITLE:	[1669468-1] Implementing Early Mobilization in the Intensive Care Unit
REFERENCE #:	20-50X
SUBMISSION TYPE:	New Project
ACTION:	DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS
DECISION DATE:	January 29, 2021
REVIEW CATEGORY:	Exemption category # 2(i)

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT A MODIFICATION APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE RE-EVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact Claire Bakewell. It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

APPENDIX F

Project Approval Letter

Los Angeles County
Board of Supervisors

Hilda L. Solis
First District

Mark Ridley-Thomas
Second District

Sheila Kuehl
Third District

Janice Hahn
Fourth District

Kathryn Barger
Fifth District

Jorge Orozco
Chief Executive Officer

Brad Spellberg, MD
Chief Medical Officer

Edgar Solis, RN
Chief Operating Officer

Annie Marquez, RN
Interim Chief Nursing Officer

1200 N. State Street
Inpatient Tower (IPT)
2nd Floor, Room C2K100
Los Angeles, CA 90033

Tel: (323) 409-2800
Fax: (323) 441-8030

To ensure access to high-quality, patient-centered, cost-effective health care to Los Angeles County residents through direct services at DHS facilities and through collaboration with community and university partners.

DATE: October 13, 2020

Department of Nursing
LAC+USC Medical Center
1200 N. State Street
Los Angeles, CA 90033

To the Institutional Review Boards of CSULA:

I am writing this letter at the request of Donnabelle Weigel to confirm that we are working with her as she commences her quality improvement project, "Implementation of Early Mobility in the ICU Setting."

I am aware that she will be conducting a survey, observational study, and data extraction of documented mobility activities using de-identified medical records from the Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU) at LAC+USC Medical Center. Ms. Weigel will have approval to do such procedures for as long as she has IRB approval to do so.

I also confirm that employees, here at LAC+USC Medical Center, will participate in the recruitment or selection of participants. Staff in the MICU will intervene with patients by performing procedures to promote early mobility. Ms. Weigel and her quality improvement team will facilitate personnel who will execute early mobility procedures.

If any unanticipated problems or adverse events are to occur, it is up to Ms. Weigel to report these events to the IRB at CSULA and the LAC+USC Chief Nursing Officer / designee as promptly as possible.

Ms. Weigel's quality improvement project will be a valuable contribution to the improvement of our patients, and we will be happy to support her in this endeavor.

Sincerely,

[Redacted signature]

Annie Marquez, RN, MSN

APPENDIX G
PDSA Cycle WORKSHEET

Objective:

1. Plan: Plan the test, including a plan for collecting data.

Questions and predictions:

Who, what, where, when:

Plan for collecting data:

2. Do: Run the test on a small scale.

Describe what happened. What data did you collect? What observations did you make?

3. Study: Analyze the results and compare them to your predictions.

Summarize and reflect on what you learned:

4. Act: Based on what you learned from the test, make a plan for your next step.

Determine what modifications you should make — adapt, adopt, or abandon:

Note: Modified from the IHI's QI. Essentials Toolkit: PDSA Worksheet. Retrieved <http://www.ihl.org/resources/Pages/Tools/PlanDoStudyActWorksheet.aspx>